

AN INVESTIGATION ON FACTORS INFLUENCING FOR TURN-AWAY OF IT PROFESSIONALS IN SRI LANKA

Dharshika Pothuwewa¹, Lasith Gunawardena²

¹*University of Sri Jayewardenepura, dharshikapothuwewa@gmail.com*

²*University of Sri Jayewardenepura, lasith@sjp.ac.lk*

Introduction

Background

Within the last few decades, the IT industry has seen significant growth across nations. Consequently, the importance of the IT professionals continues to grow. However, below the promise, there are frustrations creeping in. Rothberg (2006) states that as many as 50 percent of the US IT workforce has considered changing jobs. Similarly Joseph et al. (2007) too state that as many as two-thirds of IT professionals tend to leave the IT profession. Turnover itself is a serious problem for organizations, it is even more crucial when it comes to turn-away.

According to Joseph and Ang (2001) and Paré and Tremblay (2007), turnover is where the IT professionals move to another company while remaining in the IT area, while turn-away is where they abandon the IT area by moving to another functional area within their original company or in another company.

Research Problem and Objectives

Authors such as Ang and Slaughter (2000); Joia and Mangia (2017); Nelson et al., (2001) and Shropshire and Kadlec (2012) state that turn-away being a considerably different phenomenon is not well understood nor much researched unlike turnover, hence exists a knowledge gap. This study investigates what are the factors that may cause turn-away in the IT sector, in the Sri Lankan context. The research objectives are to identify factors

that cause turn-away and to identify the patterns between the identified factors and turn-away behaviour amongst IT professionals in Sri Lanka.

Methodology

Given the exploratory nature of the research purpose, a qualitative approach is adopted; without following existing theories or predetermined hypothesis. IT professionals who have turned away to other areas within their original organizations or in a different company are considered here.

Potential individuals were selected based on referrals and the snowball technique. Guided by a semi structured questionnaire five in-depth interviews were carried out and recorded followed by a data-driven thematic analysis.

The transcriptions were read repeatedly to properly be familiarized with the data. Consequently an initial list of interesting ideas could be generated which was then systematically converted to a list of initial codes. Coding was done manually using highlighters, colored pens and notes on the printed data set and then data were organized into meaningful groups under codes. These codes were sorted into potential themes using a table. Refining the significance of each potential theme and confirming their coherence with the data, the thematic map is presented.

Results and Discussion

The analysis revealed six main themes: job dissatisfaction, new opportunities, desire to gather new experiences and face challenges, intentional prior preparation, past experience and reason to choose IT. A model is proposed to illustrate the findings.

A strong indication of job dissatisfaction due to insufficient pay and exhaustion was obvious. The causes for dissatisfaction are not discussed further as it is a separate research area beyond the scope of this research. However job dissatisfaction with the IT profession could be seen as a major

Figure 1. SEQ Figure * ARABIC 1. Proposed Thematic Model

reason to leave the IT profession as discussed by authors such as Scholtz et al. (2019). On the contrary, some authors like Ramos and Joia (2013) have found it not to be a major reason.

Some have turned away while remaining in their respective organizations with the emergence of new opportunities from within. According to Reich and Kaarst-brown (1999; 2003), organizations value these ex-IT professionals.

The need to gain new experiences, the passion to learn and willingness to accept challenges too have diverted their career paths in different directions. In several instances participants have emphasized the fact that they like to take the challenges and broaden their experiences.

Sometimes they have intentionally prepared themselves prior to actually turning away. Authors such as Joia and Mangia (2017) and Ramos and Joia (2011;2014) (cited in Joia, Fontenelle & Assis, 2019) too have discussed the two aforementioned factors respectively.

In fact each one of them have acquired university degrees specializing in IT. It was interesting to find out what encouraged them to direct their higher education and hence the profession towards the IT sector. The two contrasting ideas were: availability of employment opportunities and

passion towards IT. Perception of availability of employment opportunities encourages individuals to join the IT sector despite their actual passion towards it. Expectations or attractiveness seen prior to actually working as an IT professional and how well one realizes them later during his IT career can be quite complicated to be clearly understood beforehand. Consequently lack of actual interest or passion towards IT can eventually result in the individual leaving the IT profession somewhere down his career path. It shows that initial interest towards IT, or in other words the reason to choose the IT sector, can have a significant impact on professionals to turn-away later.

Conclusion

Summary and Major Findings

This paper depicts six main themes and their connection with the phenomenon through inductive thematic analysis. Compared with available literature they show consistencies as well as inconsistencies. However one theme can be seen as new knowledge; namely the theme “reason to choose” which is about why individuals have chosen to direct their careers in the IT field in the first place. It was evident that this can have significant impact on how the individual perceives his occupation or experience during mid-career. This area has not been discussed previously.

Theoretical and Managerial Implications

These findings contribute to enhance the literature on the subject. On the other hand it aids to improve basically the quality of IT career management and IT staff management in ways beneficial to both individuals and organizations.

Limitations and Future Work

Due to practical shortcomings one of the planned interviews had to be forgone. Moreover one interviewee was in the process of turning away during the time of the interview, but later he could not undergo that change.

Future work is needed to test and enhance the findings of this research as well as to make detailed comparisons with extant literature.

References

Ang, S. and Slaughter, S. A. (2000) 'The Missing Context of Information Technology Personnel: A Review and Future Directions for Research', *Framing the Domains of IT Management : Projecting the future through the past*, pp. 305–327.

Joia, L. A. and Mangia, U. (2017) 'Career transition antecedents in the information technology area', *Information Systems Journal*, 27(1), pp. 31–57. doi: 10.1111/isj.12087.

Joia, L. A. and Sily De Assis, Fontenelle, M. (2019) 'Motivations for the IT Professional Turnaway Intention : A Delphi Approach', *Information Systems Management*. Taylor & Francis, 36(3), pp. 228–242. doi: 10.1080/10580530.2019.1625239.

Joseph, D. *et al.* (2007) 'Turnover of Information Technology Professionals: A Narrative Review , Meta-Analytic Structural Equation Modeling , and Model Development.', *MIS Quaterly*, 31(3), pp. 547–577.

Joseph, D. and Ang, S. (2001) 'The Threat-Rigidity Model of Professional Obsolescence and Its Impact on Occupational Mobility Behaviors of IT Professionals.', in *ICIS 2001 Proceedings*, p. 73.

Nelson, K. M., Darais, K. M., Buche, M., & Rice, S. (2001). Identifying the constructs of IT personnel transition. *Proceedings of the Americas Conference on Information Systems*, Boston, MA, 7

Paré, G. and Tremblay, M. (2007) 'The Influence of High-Involvement Human Resources Practices, Procedural Justice, Organizational Commitment, and Citizenship Behaviors on Information Technology Professionals' Turnover Intentions.', *Group & Organization Management*, 32(3), pp. 326–357. doi: 10.1177/1059601106286875.

Ramos, E. and Joia, L. A. (2013) 'An investigation into turn-away among information technology professionals in Brazil', *Journal of High Technology Management Research*. Elsevier Inc., 24(1), pp. 30–41. doi:

10.1016/j.hitech.2013.02.005.

Reich, B. H. and Kaarst-brown, M. L. (1999) ‘" Seeding the line ": Understanding the transition from IT to non-IT careers’, *MIS Quarterly*, pp. 337–364.

Reich, B.H. and Kaarst-Brown, M.L., 2003. Creating social and intellectual capital through IT career transitions. *The Journal of Strategic Information Systems*, 12(2), pp.91-109.

Rothberg, D. (2006) *Hefty turnover anticipated among IT workforce*. Available at: www.eweek.com/it-management/hefty-turnover-anticipated-among-it-workforce. (Accessed: 24 July 2020).

Scholtz, B.M., Van Belle, J.P., Njenga, K., Serenko, A. and Palvia, P., 2019. The role of job satisfaction in turnover and turn-away intention of IT staff in South Africa. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Information, Knowledge, and Management*, 14, pp.077-097.

Shropshire, J. and Kadlec, C. (2012) ‘I ’ m Leaving the IT Field : the Impact of Stress , Job Insecurity , and Burnout on IT Professionals’, *International Journal of Information and Communication Technology Research*, 2(1), pp. 6–16.